

The Influence of Islamic Human Development and Economic Growth on Poverty Levels in South Sumatra Province

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to determine and analyze the influence of Islamic human development and economic growth on poverty rates in South Sumatra Province. This study was conducted in 17 regencies / cities in South Sumatra Province for the period 2014 - 2023. The analysis technique uses panel data regression with the help of the Eviews 12 application with hypothesis testing using the t-test and F-test. Based on the results of the model accuracy test, it is known that the best model in this study is the Random Effect Model (REM). The results of the study indicate that Islamic human development has a negative and significant effect on poverty rates, economic growth has a negative and significant effect on poverty rates, simultaneously Islamic human development and economic growth have a significant effect on poverty rates in South Sumatra Province.

KEYWORDS: Islamic Human Development, Economic Growth, Poverty Rate

INTRODUCTION

Poverty is one of the main problems faced by developing countries including Indonesia, especially in South Sumatra Province. Poverty is not only related to lack of income or inability to meet basic needs, but also includes social injustice, limited access to education, health, and decent employment opportunities. Various efforts have been made to reduce poverty rates, but this problem remains a major challenge because poverty is multidimensional. This means that poverty is closely related to income inequality, limited access to resources, and the social environment that affects the economic structure of society. (Ardian et al., 2021)

According to the Central Bureau of Statistics, the problem of poverty is increasingly complex due to a number of causes, such as unequal distribution of infrastructure, low quality of education, and limited employment opportunities in rural areas. Many residents in remote areas face difficulties in gaining access to decent schools, basic health services, and other public facilities that play an important role in improving the quality of life. This has an impact on limited skills and health, which ultimately affects people's ability to get stable jobs and sufficient income (Padriyansyah & Syahputera, 2022)

In line with this, poverty in South Sumatra Province cannot be separated from various economic factors, such as uneven economic growth, high unemployment rates and limited access to education and health services. Uneven economic growth has resulted in income inequality between regions, with urban areas often enjoying better welfare than rural areas. Although South Sumatra Province has great natural resource potential, dependence on certain sectors, such as agriculture and mining, has not been able to create stable and equal employment opportunities throughout the region. (MPDSCS Todaro, 2003, p. 35) The high poverty rate in South Sumatra Province is also influenced by limited infrastructure and economic accessibility in several areas. Many rural areas still have difficulty in obtaining adequate transportation facilities, thus hampering the distribution of goods and services and community access to wider economic opportunities. In addition, limited access to capital for small and medium enterprises (SMEs) makes it increasingly difficult for groups with economic limitations to improve their standard of living. This condition exacerbates the economic gap between groups with access to resources and those who are less fortunate, making poverty alleviation efforts increasingly challenging. (Sumarto & de Silva, 2014) According to the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), data on poverty levels in South Sumatra Province for 2014-2023 are as follows:

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Figure 1. Poverty Level in South Sumatra Province 2014-2023

Figure 1 shows that poverty rate data has consistently decreased from 13.62% in 2014 to 11.78% in 2023, which is a decrease of 1.84%. This decrease shows the success of various poverty alleviation programs, such as social assistance, increasing access to education and health, and creating jobs. However, this gradual decrease also indicates that there are still challenges faced, especially in rural and remote areas that often have limited access to services and economic opportunities. In maintaining this downward trend, continuous efforts are needed in equalizing infrastructure and improving the quality of life (Central Statistics Agency of South Sumatra Province, 2023a)

In addition to reducing poverty rates, the Human Development Index (HDI) is also an important indicator in assessing the welfare and quality of life of the community. The Human Development Index also covers three main aspects, namely education, health, and a decent standard of living that directly affect an individual's ability to access jobs and participate in economic activities. (Mudrajad Kuncoro, 1997, p. 67). The concept of human development in the conventional Human Development Index (HDI) does not fully represent Islamic values because it is not based on the principles of Maqashid Syariah. Therefore, in measuring the welfare of society in areas where the majority of the population is Muslim, a more appropriate approach is needed, namely through the concept of Islamic Human Development (IHD). This concept is developed based on five dimensions of Maqashid Syariah, namely the dimensions of religion (ad-dien), soul (an-nafs), reason (al-'aql), descendants (an-nasl), and wealth (al-maal). Measuring human development with the IHD approach is considered more holistic than the conventional HDI because it includes spiritual, moral, and material aspects that are in line with the goals of Islamic law. Although officially the Province of South Sumatra still uses the HDI as the main indicator in assessing development achievements during the 2014–2023 period, the Islamic Human Development approach provides a more comprehensive perspective in viewing the welfare of society in an Islamic way. (MB Hendie Anto, 2013) According to the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), the Human Development Index data in South Sumatra Province for 2014-2023 is as follows:

Figure 2. Human Development Index in South Sumatra Province 2014-2023

Figure 2 shows that the Human Development Index (HDI) increased from 66.75% in 2014 to 73.18% in 2023, which is an increase of 6.43%, indicating improvements in health, education, and people's living standards. This increase is due to various programs that extend life expectancy, improve access and quality of education, and increase per capita income through economic growth. (Central Statistics Agency of South Sumatra Province, 2023b) Economic growth is also an important indicator in

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development efforts to achieve higher levels of prosperity, and is a major component in poverty reduction.(Asmananta et al., 2022)

Economic growth is the process of increasing a country's capacity to produce goods and services over time, which is usually measured by the increase in Gross Domestic Product (GDP). With sustainable economic growth, the country should be able to improve people's standard of living, create jobs, and improve the overall quality of life. However, the phenomenon of economic growth is often uneven. This unevenness creates inequality, so that some people, especially low-income groups or those living in remote areas, do not feel the benefits directly. Therefore, economic growth needs to be more inclusive so that its benefits can be enjoyed by all groups in society, so that it can reduce poverty and improve welfare evenly.(Sumitro Djojohadikusumo, 1994, p. 2) According to the Central Bureau of Statistics, Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) is the total value of goods and services produced in a certain area and within a certain time without considering ownership indicators. The annual increase in Gross Domestic Product (GDP) results in economic growth in a region, which indicates an increase in goods and services in the region and this increase in GDP is carried out at constant prices.(bps.go.id, 2024) The following is Economic Growth Data in South Sumatra Province 2014-2023:

Figure 3. Economic Growth in South Sumatra Province 2014-2023

Figure 1.3 shows that the increase in economic growth data in South Sumatra Province from 4.79% in 2014 to 5.08% in 2023, with a total increase of 0.29%, this can be caused by several factors, including production growth, expenditure growth, trade balance, rice production, rubber production, cement procurement, household consumption expenditure per capita and government capital expenditure. Overall, these factors contribute to increasing economic growth in South Sumatra Province.(Moh Wahyu Yulianto, 2023)

Various studies related to Islamic human development and economic growth on poverty levels include:(Sri Nurlyli and Jumarni, 2022)The results of his research show that Islamic human development has an effect on poverty levels, but this is different from research conducted by(Hayatuzahrah Taqiyyah & Sri Muljaningsih, 2024)where the research results show that Islamic human development has no effect on poverty levels. Then the research conducted by(Widya Widya et al., 2023)which explains that economic growth has an effect on poverty levels, but this is different from research conducted by(Asmananta et al., 2022)where the research results show that economic growth has no effect on poverty levels.

The main problem discussed in this study is whether Islamic human development and economic growth have an effect on the poverty rate in South Sumatra Province? Based on this, the objectives to be achieved in this study are to determine and analyze the effect of Islamic human development and economic growth on the poverty rate in South Sumatra Province.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Islamic Human Development

Islamic Human Development (IHD) is a conceptual approach to assessing human development based on holistic Islamic values. Unlike conventional development approaches that emphasize material aspects, Islamic Human Development encompasses worldly and hereafter welfare by considering spiritual, social, and economic dimensions. One measurement approach to this concept is the Islamic Human Development Index (I-HDI), which is designed to reflect the level of human welfare by referring to the five main principles of Maqashid Syariah. According to Imam al-Syatibi, the main objectives of sharia (maqashid syariah) consist of five important elements, namely: maintaining religion (ad-dien), soul (an-nafs), reason (al-'aql), descendants (an-nasl), and

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property (al-maal). These five elements are considered basic human needs that must be met to achieve true welfare in the Islamic perspective. (Lubis et al., 2022, p. 2)

Economic growth

Economic growth is a very important phenomenon in the study of economics, because it is directly related to improving the welfare of society. In general, economic growth is defined as an increase in a country's capacity to produce more goods and services over time, which can increase per capita income and reduce poverty levels. This term was first introduced by Simon Kuznets, who stated that economic growth is a process that allows a country to increase its capacity to provide various types of economic goods to its population. This process is influenced by factors such as technological progress, institutional development, and changes in the philosophy underlying the country's economic policy. (Mahendra, 2016)

Poverty

Poverty is a condition in which a person is unable to meet the basic needs for a decent life. These basic needs include food, clothing, housing, health, education, employment, clean water, the right to a safe environment, and participation in social life with dignity. (Moh. Arif Novriansyah, 2018)

Research Conceptual Framework

To understand in general terms the influence of Islamic human development and economic growth on poverty levels in South Sumatra Province, you can see the following conceptual framework image.

Figure 4. Research Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

M. Umer Chapra explained that Islamic economic development does not only focus on holistic welfare that includes material, social, and spiritual aspects. This development concept is based on the values of Maqasid Syariah which are reflected in Islamic Human Development. Thus, poverty alleviation can not only be achieved through conventional economic policies, but also by integrating Islamic values in Development that focuses on social justice and more equitable community empowerment. (Sri Nurlayli and Jumarni, 2022) which proves that the Islamic Human Development Index has a significant influence on poverty levels. Then the research conducted by (Hayatuzahrah Taqiyah & Sri Muljaningsih, 2024) shows that the Islamic Human Development Index has a negative and insignificant influence on poverty levels.

H1 : Islamic human development has a positive influence on poverty levels

High and sustainable economic growth is expected to reduce poverty levels in society. In this case, economic growth is not only seen in terms of increasing national output, but also in terms of a more even distribution of wealth. Economic growth that is not balanced with equality will result in social inequality which can actually worsen the problem of poverty. Therefore, it is important to ensure that the results of economic growth can be felt by all levels of society, especially the most vulnerable groups. (Kuznets, 1955). (Widya Widya et al., 2023) which proves that economic growth has a positive and significant influence on poverty levels. Then the research conducted by (Berlianantiya et al., 2024) shows that economic growth does not have a significant effect on poverty levels.

H2: Economic growth has a positive effect on poverty levels.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research was conducted in 17 regencies/cities in South Sumatra Province during the period 2014-2023. The analysis technique used in this study is multiple linear regression analysis of panel data using the Eviews 12 application, starting with testing the accuracy of the model between the Common Effect Model, Fixed Effect Model and Random Effect Model through the chow test

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and hausman test. The test is continued with the classical assumption test including the normality test, multicollinearity test and heteroscedasticity test. Hypothesis testing is carried out using the t test and F test.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This research began with a test of the model's accuracy using the Chow test with the results as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Chow Test

Redundant Fixed Effects Tests
Equation: Untitled
Cross-section fixed effects test

Effects Test	Statistics	df	Prob.
Cross-section F	83.005680	(16,149)	0.0000
Cross-section Chi-square	385.372428	16	0.0000

Source: Field research data processed, 2025

Based on table 1, it is known that the probability value of Cross-section F is 0.0000 which means it is smaller than 0.05. This shows that there are significant differences between individuals (cross-section), so the Fixed Effect model is more appropriate to use compared to the Common Effect.

Further analysis will be conducted to compare the Fixed Effect Model with the Random Effect Model through the Hausman Test as can be seen in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Hausman test

Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test
Equation: Untitled
Cross-section random effects test

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. df	Prob.
Random cross section	4.127289	2	0.1270

Source: Field research data processed, 2025

Based on table 2, the results of the Hausman test show that the Chi-Square value is 4.127289 with a probability of 0.1270, meaning it is greater than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the Random Effect Model (REM) is more appropriate to use in this study because the individual effect is proven not to be significantly correlated with the independent variable.

The next test is the classical assumption test which is a prerequisite for the regression test. Based on data processing, the following normality test results were obtained.

Figure 5 Normality Test

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Based on Figure 5, it shows that the Jarque-Bera value is 4.488981 with a probability (p-value) of 0.105933. This means that the probability value is greater than the significance level of 0.05, so H_0 is accepted, which means that the residuals are normally distributed. Thus, it can be concluded that the residual model meets the assumption of normality.

The test was continued with a multicollinearity test with the results as can be seen in table 3 below.

Table 3. Multicollinearity Test Results

	Islamic Human Development	Economic Growth
Islamic Human Development	1,000,000	0.116615
Economic Growth	0.116615	1,000,000

Source: Field research data processed, 2025

Based on table 3 shows that the correlation value between the variables of Islamic Human Development and Economic Growth is 0.1166. This value indicates that the relationship between the two independent variables is very weak and far below the threshold of 0.85. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity between the independent variables.

The classical assumption test was continued with a heteroscedasticity test with results as can be seen in the following 4.

Table 4. Results of Heteroscedasticity Test

Dependent Variable: ABS_RES

Method: Heteroscedasticity (Cross-section random effects)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	2.431392	0.536873	4.528801	0.0000
Islamic Human Development (X1)	-0.008125	0.012414	-0.654512	0.5137
Economic Growth (X2)	-0.042151	0.033459	-1.259796	0.2095

Source: Field research data processed, 2025

Based on table 4 shows that the heteroscedasticity test with the absolute residual value regression method (ABS_RES), it was obtained that the probability value for the Islamic Human Development variable (X1) was 0.5137 and for the Economic Growth variable (X2) was 0.2095. Because both probability values are greater than 0.05, it can be concluded that there are no symptoms of heteroscedasticity in the model.

After the classical assumption test was fulfilled, a multiple linear regression analysis was carried out using the Random Effect Model (REM) as shown in Table 5 below.

Table 5. Multiple Linear Regression Test Results - Random Effect Model

Dependent Variable: Poverty Level

Method: Panel EGLS (Cross-section random effects)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	12.73055	0.818397	15.55548	0.0000
Islamic Human Development (X1)	-0.013876	0.015513	0.894508	0.0324
Economic Growth (X2)	-0.006972	0.036203	-0.192593	0.0415
Effects Specification			SD	Rho
Random cross section			2.451230	0.8944
Idiosyncratic random			0.842125	0.1056
Weighted Statistics				

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Root MSE	0.840361	R-squared	0.005112
Mean dependent variable	1.428609	Adjusted R-squared	0.069477
SD dependent var	0.848793	SE of regression	0.847966
Sum squared residual	118.6427	F-statistic	0.423907
Durbin-Watson stat	0.519601	Prob(F-statistic)	0.004516
Unweighted Statistics			
R-squared	-0.038703	Mean dependent variable	13.13411
Sum squared residual	1159.206	Durbin-Watson stat	0.053180

Source: Field research data processed, 2024

Based on Table 5, the regression line equation can be compiled as follows.

$$\text{Poverty Rate} = 12.73055 - 0.013876 X_1 - 0.006972 X_2$$

The constant value is 12.73055, meaning that when the independent variables (Islamic Human Development and Economic Growth) are 0, the Poverty Rate is only 12.73055. The regression coefficient value of the Islamic Human Development variable is negative 0.013876, meaning that every 1% increase in Islamic Human Development will increase the poverty rate by 0.013876. The regression coefficient value of the Economic Growth variable is negative 0.006972, meaning that if Economic Growth decreases by 1%, it will decrease the poverty rate by 0.006972, assuming that other independent variables remain constant.

The Islamic human development variable has a coefficient of -0.013876, a t-value of 0.894508, and a probability value (p-value) of 0.0324 < 0.05, which means that the hypothesis is accepted so that it can be explained that partially Islamic human development has a negative and significant effect on the poverty rate in South Sumatra. (Chapra, 2011) explains that Islamic economic development does not only focus on holistic welfare which includes material, social, and spiritual aspects. This development concept is based on the values of Maqasid Syariah which are reflected in Islamic human development. Thus, poverty alleviation can not only be achieved through conventional economic policies, but also by integrating Islamic values in development that focuses on social justice and more equitable community empowerment. The results of this study are in accordance with research (Khairul Fadilah, 2019) and (Aiu Viollani et al., 2022) which shows that Islamic human development has a significant negative effect on poverty.

The economic growth variable has a coefficient of -0.006972, a t-value of -0.192593, and a p-value of 0.0415 < 0.05, which means that the hypothesis is accepted so that it can be explained that partially economic growth has a negative and significant effect on the poverty rate in South Sumatra. (MP Todaro, 2019), which underlines that in developing countries, economic growth must be accompanied by inclusive development policies, which target structural poverty alleviation. The results of this study are in accordance with research (Aiu Viollani et al., 2022), which states that although economic growth plays an important role in reducing poverty, its impact can be reduced if the results of development are not evenly distributed.

The F-statistic value is 0.423907 with a probability value (Prob. F-statistic) of 0.004516 < 0.05, which means that the hypothesis is accepted so that it can be explained that together the variables of Islamic human development and economic growth have a significant effect on the poverty rate in South Sumatra. The Adjusted R-squared value is 0.069477. If converted into a percentage, the value is around 6.95%. This means that the independent variables, namely Islamic Human Development and economic growth, together are able to explain the variability of the poverty rate in South Sumatra Province by 6.95%. The rest, which is 93.05%, is explained by other variables outside the model or by other factors not included in the study. The research conducted by (Aiu Viollani et al., 2022) shows that simultaneously the variables of Islamic human development and economic growth have a significant influence on poverty levels.

CONCLUSIONS, LIMITATIONS, AND SUGGESTIONS

Islamic human development has a negative and significant effect on poverty levels in South Sumatra. Economic growth has a negative and significant effect on poverty levels in South Sumatra. Islamic human development and economic growth have a negative and significant effect on poverty levels in South Sumatra

This study is limited to the variables of Islamic human development and economic growth as independent variables and the limited years of observation. Then the study was only conducted in South Sumatra Province. Therefore, for further researchers, it is recommended to add other variables that can affect the level of poverty, such as income inequality, the informal sector, or other

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external factors that can provide deeper insight. In addition, further research can expand the sample or extend the analysis period to obtain more general results and expand the object of research, namely in Indonesia.

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